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IS E-ADMINISTRATION A CHALLENGE FOR THE PUBLIC ADMINISTRATION OR NOT? CASE STUDY OF BIHOR COUNTY, ROMANIA

Abstract: *The Internet or E-administration are generally associated with databases, management information systems, or expert-systems. In today's society, they are associated with transparency, interactivity, flexibility or integration. All these things have changed the way in which we understand the public administration but they are also challenges for the public administration in Romania. The contemporary society is increasingly focused on digitalization, for the purpose of adjusting the public administration services to the citizens' needs. In this paper, the author analyzes whether e-administration in 2024 is a challenge for the public administration in Bihor County, Romania. The practice and events from recent years have demonstrated that territorial administrative units in Romania need to use platforms and software programs in promoting their services and relations with citizens, and ensuring the efficiency, effectiveness and transparency of their public administration activities at the local level. In this context, the author analyzes E-administration at the level of the main municipalities and territorial administrative units (communes) in Bihor County. The author seeks response to the question whether E-administration is a challenge for the local administration authorities or a normal activity in Bihor County. In that regard, the paper aims to present the challenges encountered by the territorial administrative units from the perspective of institutional, financial and human resources, as well as from the citizens' point of view (i.e. citizens access to E-administration). The research data were collected from the documentary sources posted at the websites of the territorial administrative units of four municipalities and three communes in Bihor County.*

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In the author's opinion, E-administration is necessary and unavoidably in the contemporary society. It is a solution for an effective communication between the citizen and the administration. But, given that territorial administrative units face different challenges in the process of implementing e-administration, there is a need for standardization of the official websites of the territorial administrative units and financial support by the Government.

Keywords: public administration, Internet, E-administration, digitalization, citizens, Bihor County.

1. Introduction and methodology

The contemporary society is constantly changing. In such circumstances, the public administration is obliged to adapt to the ever-changing needs and demands of the society. Public institutions increasingly use digital technologies and platforms to support their mission (Mergel, 2012: 3). In today's society, the Internet or E-administration are generally associated with databases, management information systems, or expert-systems, which should provide the public administration services to the citizens in line with the principles of transparency, interactivity, flexibility or integration. In this paper, the author presents the data collected through a content analysis of the official websites of some territorial administrative units in Bihor County, Romania, and discusses to what extent the local territorial administration units have managed to provide public administration services to their citizens. The methodology of the conducted research includes content analysis of the official websites of some territorial administrative units in Bihor County which have been used to promote the relationship between the local public administration units and the citizens. The provided analysis focuses on the state of affairs in the local public administration, with specific reference to digitalization of public administration services in the Bihor County. The author presents the attained level of development in territorial administrative units (municipalities and communes), and the advantages and disadvantages of digitization in the local administration and its need to quickly adapt and respond to the demands of the society.

In this context, the objectives of this paper are twofold. The first objective is to analyze the relationship between the citizen and the public administration from the perspective of digitization of public services at the level of local administrative units. The second objective is to observe the challenges encountered by the territorial administrative units in the process of implementing e-administration. To this effect, the paper provides a comparative

analysis of four municipalities from Bihor County (Oradea, Beiuș, Marghita, and Salonta) and three territorial administrative units (communes) in the vicinity of Oradea (Sânmartin, Sântandrei, and Nojorid).

2. E-administration in a national and local context

In Europe, the Nordic countries have a long legal history of open access to government information, which is constitutionally acknowledged as the principle of publicity. This principle can be associated with the high level of trust and consensual traditions prevailing in these countries (Erkkilä, 2012: 38).

In Romania, e-government has been the subject matter of discussion since 2010, when the traditional administrative system was transformed into a transparent public administration system available through the Ghiseul.ro platform.¹ We have to recognize the fact that public administration today can hardly be imagined without institutional cooperation and without digital networks, which are the means used to facilitate the relationship between the public administration and the citizen. The COVID-19 pandemic period clearly demonstrated that territorial administrative units in Romania need to use platforms and application in promoting their services and relations with citizens, and ensuring the efficiency, effectiveness and transparency of their public administration activities at the local level. The pandemic period proved that those territorial administrative units that had an online communication with their citizen managed to adapt in a short time and continue providing their services, which resulted in the regular collection of taxes and fees, the ongoing activities of public officials and maintaining the relations with the citizens through e-government/e-administration.

These practice and events have demonstrated that territorial administrative units in Romania need to use platforms and software programs in providing their services, promoting their relations with citizens, and ensuring the efficiency, effectiveness and transparency of their public administration activities at the local level. In this regard, the County of Bihor is a model of good practice, particularly the Municipality of Oradea. Considering that the digitalization of public administration services in the territorial administrative units in Bihor County has shown different results, we will try to analyze the current state of affairs in the implementation of e-administration/government in 2024.

¹ Ghilseul.ro is the national electronic system for online payment and obtaining certain documents online, provided by the Romanian Government (See: <https://www.ghilseul.ro/ghilseul/public/>).

3. Case study: The situation in Bihor County municipalities and communes

Bihor County is located in the western part of Romania, on the border with Hungary. It covers the area 7,544 km², and has the population of over 616,000 inhabitants (2020). It comprises 101 territorial administrative units: 4 municipalities, 6 cities, and 91 communes.² The conducted research included the collection of data and comparative analysis of the official websites of the territorial administrative units from Bihor County: four municipalities (Oradea, Beiuș, Marghita, and Salonta) and three communes in the vicinity of Oradea (Sânmartin, Sântandrei, and Nojorid). This part of the paper presents the research results.

3.1. The situation in municipalities

This part of the paper presents the content analysis based on the data collected from the official websites of four municipalities: Oradea, Beiuș, Marghita, and Salonta.

3.1.1. Oradea Municipality

The City of Oradea is located in the north western part of Romania, near the border with Hungary. It covers the area of 115 km² and has over 200.000 inhabitants (2021 census). The Municipality of Oradea³ is a model of good practice in local public administration. Citizens may easily access the official website of the Municipality of Oradea by a simple click, and use a variety of online services for citizens and business entities (e.g. tax information and tax payment, parking services, submission and issuance of personal documents, online requests, mobile applications, information services about the urban planning, utilities, recycling, local elections, etc.) (see photos below).⁴

²Consiliul Județean Bihor (2024). Bihor County: Administrative-teritorial Profile; <https://www.cjbihor.ro/despre-bihor/profil-administrativ-teritorial/> (accessed on 2.09.2024).

³See: the official website of the Municipality of Oradea; <https://oradea.ro/> (accessed on 2.09.2024).

⁴See: Oradea online services: <https://oradea.ro/servicii-online/>, For citizens: <https://oradea.ro/pentru-cetateni/>; For companies: <https://oradea.ro/pentru-firme/>; For tourists: <https://oradea.ro/turist-in-oradea/>; City Hall information: <https://oradea.ro/primaria-oradea/> (accessed on 2.09.2024).

Photo 1: Oradea Municipality website
Source: <https://oradea.ro/>

Photo 2: Online services - For citizens
Source: <https://oradea.ro/pentru-cetateni>

Photo 3: Online services For the community
Source: <https://oradea.ro/pentru-cetateni/>

Photo 4: Online services (in Hungarian)
Source: <https://oradea.ro/hu/online-szolgáltatások>

Photo 5: Oradea City Report app

Source: <https://oradea.ro/primaria-oradea/> (accessed in 2.09.2024)

The official website of also offers different information on the Oradea City Hall activities (financial information, procurements, announcements on different activities, etc.), as well as online information in English and in Hungarian language (in the Municipality of Oradea there is a community of over 20% Hungarian citizens). In addition to the online platform, the Municipality of Oradea has a mobile application called *Oradea City Report*, which enables citizens to report incidents and send notifications to local public service operators (local transport, police, environment, water, heating, electric energy companies, etc.).⁵ However, this application is not perfect and one is unlikely to receive a response even after 60 days. In this regard, there is certainly room for improvement in terms of transparency and the public administration services' response to citizens complaints.

3.1.2. Beiuș Municipality

The City of Beiuș is one of the oldest cities in Bihor County, located in the southeast of the county, 62 km from Oradea, at the foot of the Apuseni Mountains. It covers the area of 25 km², with the population of about 10.000 inhabitants. The official website of the Municipality of Beiuș shows that the relations between the local administration and the citizens also takes place online. The website contains information on public announcements and procurements, local taxes, police, projects and public debates, online payment services, urban planning, investments, sanitation services, elections, petitions, EU projects, etc. (see photos below).⁶ However, the website is not available in

⁵ The website of Oradea City Hall: <https://oradea.ro/primaria-oradea/> (accessed on 2.09.2024)

⁶ The official website of the Municipality of Beiuș: <https://www.municipiulbeius.ro/>

any international language, which would be beneficial for the business environment and investment in th Photos 6, 7,8, 9, 10: Beiuș Municipality website

Photos 6, 7, 8, 9, 10: Beiuș Municipality website

Source: <https://www.municipiulbeius.ro/>(accessed on 2.09.2024) is region.

3.1.3. Marghita Municipality

The Municipality of Marghita is located in the north of Bihor County, on the right bank of the Barcău River, between the Viișoarai Hills and the Barcău Plain. It cover an area of 373 hectares and has a population of 13,573 inhabit-

(accessed on 2.09.2024)

ants. An insight into the official website of the Marghita Municipality shows that online interaction between the local public administration and the citizen covers online payment of taxes and fees, obtaining heavy transport permits, different information of public interest (budget, expenditures, audits), online forms, information about programs, strategies, EU projects, public debates, local elections, etc. (see photos below).⁷ The information is provided in Romanian, English and Hungarian (as the Hungarian community makes over 20% of the population in this municipality).

Photos 11, 12, 13: Marghita Municipality website

Source: <https://marghita.ro/> (accessed on 2.09.2024)

3.1.4. Salonta municipality

The Municipality of Salonta is the second most populous municipality in Bihor County, after the municipality of Oradea. It is located in the western part of the country, near the border with Hungary. It covers 170.04 km² and has a population of 15,792 inhabitants.

⁷The official website of the Municipality of Marghita: <https://marghita.ro/> (accessed on 2.09.2024)

The data available at the official website of the Municipality of Salonta show that online communication between the citizen and the local public administration is minimal. It largely entails online payment of taxes and fees, payment of contravention fines, and submission of online request, complaint, notification or proposals, but there is no form of response to petitions or applications. The website also provides information of public interest in Romanian and Hungarian about economy, public tenders, procurements, institutions, tourism, public announcements, debates, local elections, etc. (see photos below).⁸

Photos 14, 15: the Municipality of Salonta website

Source: <https://salonta.net/ro/> (accessed on 2.09.2024)

3.2. The situation in the communes

This part of the paper provides the analysis of data available at the official websites of three territorial administrative units (communes) in Bihor County: Sânmartin, Sântandrei, and Nojorid, which are located around the main county seat municipality – Oradea. The analysis shows to what extent these communes use online service to promote the relationship between the local public administration units and the citizens.

3.2.1. Sanmartin commune

The commune of Sânmartin is located only 5 km from the Municipality of Oradea, and has a population of 12,448 inhabitants. Within its boundaries, there are two most renowned thermal baths in Romania: the oldest *Băile 1*

⁸ The official website of the Municipality of Salonta: <https://salonta.net/ro/>; <https://salonta.net/ro/transparenta-decisionala-3/generale/> (accessed on 2.09.2024)

Mai and the most famous *Băile Felix*. The analysis of the official website of the commune of Sânmartin has brought a pleasant surprise in terms of the citizen-public administration relations. In addition to information about the local public administration bodies, the website provide information of public interest (local development strategies, urban planning, public transport, tourism, budget, projects and investments for government and EU funds, local institutions/organisations, agricultural register, public debates, etc), as well as online services (online forms; online payment of taxes, duties, fines; submission of online requests, applications, notifications) via the Registra e-Government portal, which also provides an opportunity to check online the status of check online the status of submitted requests, consult public documents, etc. The Registra portal provides information about services in Romanian, Hungarian, German, English, Russian and Serbian language, and the portal is also accessible via the Registra app (see photos below).⁹

Photos 16, 17, 18, 19: Sânmartin commune website

Source: <https://sanmartin.regista.ro/formulare>, <https://sanmartin.regista.ro/plati-online>; <https://sanmartin.regista.ro/#verificare-cereri> (accessed on 2.09.2024)

⁹The official website of Sânmartin commune: <https://sanmartin.ro/>; <https://sanmartin.regista.ro/formulare>; <https://sanmartin.regista.ro/plati-online>; <https://sanmartin.regista.ro/#verificare-cereri> (access 2.09.2024)

The commune of Sânmartin in Bihor County has approached the online relationship with the citizen in an objective and pragmatic way, providing the citizen with ways to solve problems with just a simple click. The fact that the website is accessible in five foreign languages shows that this public administration body is open to innovation and internationalization.

3.2.2. Sântandrei commune

The commune of Sântandrei is located in the western part of Bihor county, about 7 km from the city of Oradea, and has the population of 9,025 inhabitants. The analysis of the data obtained from the official website of the Sântandrei Town Hall shows that the local public administration provides information on different issues of public importance (urban planning, local election, local police, procurements, civil status, etc.) as well as an opportunity for online payment of taxes, duties and fines via the CityOn portal and submission of online requests online (see photos below).¹⁰ On the whole, the analysis of the official website shows that online communication between the local public administration and the citizens is brief and deficient as it is largely restricted to online payments. The website is accessible only in Romanian language but the CityOn platform may be used in more than 10 foreign languages.

¹⁰ The official website of Sântandrei Town Hall: <https://www.primariasantandrei.ro/>; CityOn portal <https://santandrei.cityon.ro/UAT/Module> (accessed on 2.09.2024).

Photos 20, 21, 22, 23: Sântandrei Town Hall website
 Source: <https://www.primariasantandrei.ro/>, <https://santandrei.cityon.ro/UAT/Module>
 (accessed on 2.09.2024)

3.2.3. Nojorid commune

The commune of Nojorid is located 9 km south of the municipality of Oradea, with a population of 3,038 inhabitants. The analysis of data posted on the official website of the Nojorid Town Hall shows that the local public administration authorities provide general public information (on development strategy, urban planning, investments, budget, local elections, local police, local projects, sanitation, environment, etc), The only online relationship with citizens is the opportunity of online payment of taxes, duties and fees via the CityOn portal, where citizens may also submit online requests (see photos below).¹¹ The website is available only in Romanian. Unfortunately, it is not regularly updated and there are inaccessible and unusable sections on the website.

¹¹The official website of Sântandrei Town Hall: <https://www.primarianojorid.ro/>; CityOn portal

Photos 21, 22: Nojorid Town Hall website

Source: <https://www.primarianojorid.ro/>, <https://nojorid.cityon.ro/UAT/Module> (accessed on 2.09.2024)

4. General remarks on the provided analysis

The purpose of this analysis was to examine the actual state of affairs concerning the online relationship and communication between the citizens and the local public administration authorities in four municipalities (Oradea, Beiuș, Marghita, and Salonta) and three communes (Sânmartin, Sântandrei, and Nojorid) in Bihor County, Romania.

The analysis led to the conclusion that the Municipality of Oradea and the commune of Sânmartin have made clear efforts to develop a fair and close online relationship with the citizens, who are just a click away from resolving the specific problem. Even if there is still room for improvement, it is obvious that these two local public administration authorities have mastered the role of e-administration, responded to the challenges, and deployed open and innovative online instruments to internationalize the citizens' access to their websites.

As for the other municipalities and communes observed in this research, there is still a lot of work to be done in the development of the online relationship and communication between the citizen and the public administration. E-administration is a viable solution for establishing effective online communication with citizens. Unfortunately, many territorial administrative units in Bihor County are not ready for this online relationship. They face various challenges in the process of implementing e-administration, particularly in terms of institutional, financial and human resources. Yet, the fact that many territorial administrative units in Bihor County are not ready for e-administration does not mean that it should be abandoned. In order to institute an efficient and transparent communication between the citizen and the public administration, there is a need for good governance at the level of local territorial administrative units, the standardization and upgrading of the official websites of the territorial administrative units, and financial support by the Government aimed at enhancing the implementation of e-administration projects at the local level (Timofte, 2016: 117). It is especially relevant considering that the territorial administrative units have started recognizing the importance of promoting good governance practices, while Romanian universities have started providing academic and professional training programs on e-administration in an endeavour to cater for human resources.

5. Instead of conclusion

In the contemporary society, there is a need for digitization. In the field of public administration, there is a need to establish online relationship and efficient communication between the citizen and the public administration. The examples of good practices during the COVID-19 pandemic have demonstrated that territorial administrative units in Romania need to use online platforms and applications to promote their services and relations with citizens, and to endure the efficiency, effectiveness and transparency of their public administration activities both at the national and the local level.

One should appreciate the fact that the relationship between citizens and decision-making authorities in a democratic society may emanate in different forms, and that this relationship is subject to continuous reconfiguration and development. Public institutions have to establish quick, transparent and efficient relationship with citizens, which can easily be achieved by enabling more effective online communication. But, considering the observed challenges in the process of implementing e-administration, there is a need for institutional, financial and human resources. In that context, one should also appreciate good collaboration between local administration authorities and universities as an effort to ensure relevant human resources. But, it is also necessary to standardize and upgrade the official websites of the territorial administrative units, strengthen the institutional control mechanisms, and ensure financial support by the Government for further development of e-administration.

In response to the question posed in the title of this paper, it must be emphasized that e-administration is a challenge both for the public administration authorities (which are obliged to regularly update their websites and respond to citizens requests in a transparent, responsible and efficient manner) and for many citizens as users of e-administration platforms and services. Personally speaking, e-administration is a challenge, but in a positive sense, as it drives the author's further research in this very current area of administrative law.

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Municipality of Salonta: <https://salonta.net/ro/>

SanMartin Commune: <https://sanmartin.ro/>

Sântandrei Commune: <https://www.primariasantandrei.ro/>

Nojorid Commune: <https://www.primarianojorid.ro/>

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**ДА ЛИ ЈЕ Е-УПРАВА ИЗАЗОВ ЗА ЛОКАЛНУ ЈАВНУ УПРАВУ ИЛИ НЕ?
СТУДИЈСКИ СЛУЧАЈ ОКРУГА БИХОР, РУМУНИЈА**

Резиме

Интернет и е-управа се генерално повезују са базама података, системима за управљање информацијама или експертским системима. У савременом друштву, е-управа подразумева транспарентност, интерактивност, флексибилност и интеграцију. Иако је е-управа променила наше схватање јавне управе, она представља велики изазов за јавну управу у Румунији. Савремено друштво је све више усмерено на дигитализацију, у циљу прилагођавања услуга јавне управе потребама грађана. У овом раду ауторка анализира да ли е-управа данас представља изазов за јавну управу округа Бихор, Румунија. Пракса и догађаји из последњих година су показали да територијалне административне јединице у Румунији морају да користе онлине платформе и апликације ради унапређења својих услуга и односа са грађанима, као и обезбеђивања ефикасности, ефективности и транспарентности активности јавне управе на локалном нивоу. У том контексту, ауторка врши анализу е-управе на нивоу неколико главних општина и територијалних административних јединица округа Бихор, Румунија. Ауторка тражи одговор на питање да ли је е-управа изазов за локалне административне власти или нормална активност у округу Бихор. Рад има за циљ да прикаже изазове са којима се територијалне управне јединице сусрећу из перспективе институционалних, финансијских и људских ресурса, као и из перспективе грађана (тј. приступа е-управи). Истраживање је засновано на подацима прикупљеним из документарних извора са интернет страница општина и територијалних управних јединица у округу Бихор. По мишљењу аутора, е-управа је неопходна и незаобилазна у савременом друштву. Она је решење за ефикасну комуникацију између грађана и администрације. С обзиром да се територијалне јединице јавне управе суочавају са разним изазовима у процесу имплементације е-управе, постоји потреба за стандардизацијом званичних интернет страница локалних управних јединица и финансијском подршком државних власти.

Кључне речи: јавна управа, интернет, е-управа, дигитализација, грађани, округ Бихор (Румунија).